

COLDSPARK DRIVEN ENERGY AND COST-EFFICIENT METHANE CRACKING FOR HYDROGEN PRODUCTION

D8.3. Data Management Plan (M24)

ColdSpark® project partner	SEID AS
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Document Approval

Name	Role	Action	Date
Terje Hauan	Project Coordinator	Approved	31/05/2024

Nature of the deliverable

R	Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)	
DEM	Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs	
DEC	Websites, patent filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.	
DATA	Data sets, microdata, etc.	
DMP	Data management plan	X
Ethics	Deliverables related to ethics issues.	
SECURITY	Deliverables related to security issues	
Other	Software, technical diagrams, algorithms, models, etc.	

Dissemination level

PU	Public — fully open (automatically posted online on the Project Results platforms)	X
SEN	Sensitive — limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement	

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The ColdSpark® project will validate a novel non-thermal plasma technology to produce hydrogen at an industrial scale from methane, with a process energy efficiency of 79%, achieving a conversion rate of 85% aiming at zero CO₂ emissions. This will be achieved by designing an industrial-relevant reactor that leverages the best features of the non-thermal plasma technologies, gliding arc and corona discharge, to ensure high efficiency and scalability. The innovation addresses for the first time the critical step of matching the reactor with a pulsed power supply. It enables a perfect fine-tuning of the cracking process parameters, to find the right electron density and energy distribution in the plasma reactor, to maximise energy efficiency. The up-and-downstream gas management will be optimised to further contribute to the system’s compatibility with the existing infrastructure. The project will develop and test a novel plasma reactor at a lab scale and validate it in conjunction with the power supply at a large scale, pursuing the industry’s most power-efficient generation of hydrogen alongside high-value carbon. The technology will assess its application for both, natural gas and biomethane producers. A low energy cost (< 15 kWh/kg H₂ produced) without the need for catalysts and water, makes the proposed solution the most cost-competitive, environment-friendly, and less complex to implement. The reactor design and modularity bring lower CAPEX and OPEX and make it easily scalable and flexible. The project gathers the expertise of a mix of academic, research, and industrial partners from five countries, which bring both outstanding research and topic competence, as well as knowledge and access to the solution for end-user industries.

ColdSpark® is built on a strong consortium of 7 partners from Norway, Spain, Bulgaria, Germany, and the UK with SEID AS as a Coordinator.

More information about the project can be found at: www.coldspark.eu

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The current document is an updated version of the Data Management Plan (M6) of the ColdSpark® project. Its primary objective is to evaluate the data generated and used within the project, outline the usage of selected repositories, and ensure that all ColdSpark® partners remain dedicated to facilitating data accessibility and reusability in accordance with FAIR principles outlined in the project's Grant Agreement. Additionally, the document specifies the practices implemented to safeguard information, provides a comprehensive list of data types and formats used and generated throughout the project, and emphasizes the significance of Data Management Plan (DMP) and its subsequent updates in fostering good research data management practices. It should be noted that this document will undergo regular updates until the project's conclusion, with the final DMP update scheduled for M42 as a separate deliverable.

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Meaning
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
DMP	Data Management Plan
DM	Data Management
WP	Work Package
OR	Open Repository
PR	Project Repository
CR	Company Repository
PMO	Project Management Office

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1. DATA SUMMARY

1.1. INTRODUCTION

This version of the ColdSpark® Data Management Plan (M24) outlines which data will be produced and re-used during the project, the data management strategy, and their dissemination level. The data management plan is a living document building upon the previous version of the Data Management Plan agreed upon by the consortium at M6 and submitted as Deliverable D8.2.

The primary objective of this plan is to ensure research data is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR), which will be done through checking the following actions:

- managing research data during and after the project lifecycle according to the data management rules set for this project;
- identifying and keeping track of the types of data collected, processed, and generated;
- detailing the methodology and standards employed;
- determining whether data is confidential or can be shared or made openly accessible, along with the mechanisms for doing so;
- establishing protocols for data curation and preservation.

All project partners bear the responsibility of adhering to this plan. It will undergo continuous updates throughout the project's duration to enrich and revise existing information, as well as to address new issues or procedural changes. The subsequent official update (D8.4) is slated for submission in M42.

Structured according to the [DMP template](#) for Horizon Europe projects provided by the Commission, this plan follows the structure below:

- Data summary
- Fair data
- Other research outputs
- Allocation of resources
- Data security
- Ethics
- Other issues

1.2. WILL COLDSPARK® RE-USE ANY EXISTING DATA AND HOW

As stated in the initial version of the Data Management Plan, the ColdSpark® project strongly encourages the reuse of existing data available and all partners actively gather and process data from publicly available sources.

The reuse of data generated over the past 25 years during the coordinator's technological development endeavours, holds significant importance for the advancement of the ColdSpark® project technology. Reused data are being used by IREC CERCA in the process of life cycle assessments. Furthermore, the project harnesses data derived from previous research endeavors conducted at the University of Liverpool.

To facilitate the secure handling of reused sensitive data, we have established a dedicated repository within the ColdSpark® project's Teams platform, hosted and administered by the project coordinator. Access to this repository is organised into two levels for each Work Package. The first tier grants access to less sensitive information to all project partners, while the second tier provides access to reused data solely to partners directly engaged in the respective Work Package, ensuring that only those with an immediate need for the information can access it.

Non-sensitive reused data are incorporated into various project materials such as presentations, posters, reports, brochures, public deliverables, and audio-visual materials produced by all project partners with a leading role of EP as the partner responsible for project dissemination and the project coordinator. These materials are promptly shared on the [project repository hosted on Zenodo](#) and made accessible through the [project website](#). This ensures swift dissemination of information to stakeholders and the wider community, promoting transparency and collaboration within the ColdSpark® project.

1.3. TYPES AND FORMATS OF DATA TO BE GENERATED OR RE-USED BY THE PROJECT

The formats for generating and re-using data within the ColdSpark® project declared in the previous version of the Data management plan, remain unchanged: .xlsx, .docx, .csv, .txt, .pdf, HTML, ASPEN files, Solid edge (.par, .psm, .asm, .dft, .pwd, .dwg, .dxf, .step, .stp), OpenScad (.scad),

- SSI (*.dat), AIA (*.cdf), SSI ASCII (*.asc), SAMPL (*.SAMPL), TurboChrom (*.raw), ChemStation (*.ch), , Printed Circuit Board (PCB) use Altium designer.

For audio-visuals - JPEG, MP4, TIFF, PNG, MP3, M4V, WAVE.

Data analysis programs include Excel, MATLAB, Origin, R and Python, Diffract EVA, Renishaw Raman, Mettler Toledo TGA etc. that come along with instruments plus QtiPlot to plot the data.

1.4. PURPOSE OF THE DATA GENERATION OR RE-USE, ITS RELATION TO THE OBJECTIVES OF THE PROJECT AND USERS

1.4.1. PURPOSE

The ColdSpark® project partners use and generate both technical and commercial data. Dedicated researchers and research groups are responsible for collecting and utilising measurement and modeling data, adhering to internal data management protocols established within the project. Given the sensitive nature of most of these data, which forms the cornerstone for the future commercialisation of ColdSpark® technology, stringent measures are in place to safeguard its integrity.

Data dedicated to open access, including modelling data and techno-economic assessments, is promptly shared whenever feasible. All public deliverables are shared on the [ColdSpark® website](#) and [Zenodo community](#) upon approval by the Commission.

For sensitive deliverables, information on the work performed by the project partners will be provided on the project website without revealing sensitive details. To ensure that this information does not infringe on the IP rights of the project partners, it will be confirmed by all parties before being published in line with the project's internal procedures.

1.4.2. EXPECTED SIZE

As declared in the previous version of the DMP, a file size of raw data of less than 1 Terabyte generated during the project remains unchanged.

1.4.3. TO WHOM MIGHT YOUR DATA BE USEFUL ('DATA UTILITY'), OUTSIDE YOUR PROJECT?

The data generated within the ColdSpark® project holds value for diverse audiences, encompassing the scientific community, governmental bodies (including the European Commission, EU national bodies, and energy and environmental authorities), as well as commercial and industrial entities, including ones from the biogas sector, and the general public.

It's essential to note that research data about the development of the ColdSpark® reactor and its optimisation is treated as confidential as it is the basis for the technology's further exploitation during and after the project lifetime. As such, it will not be fully accessible to individuals or organisations outside the project. This restriction is necessary because the data includes trade secrets integral to the future commercialisation and exploitation of the technology. This confidentiality measure extends throughout the project duration and beyond, ensuring the

protection of sensitive intellectual property, which includes the registration of trademarks where applicable.

1.5. ORIGIN/PROVENANCE OF THE DATA, EITHER GENERATED OR RE-USED

All consortium partners will generate and collect data using different approaches and instruments. For instance, SEID AS will verify several parameters, such as voltage, power, frequency of the high-voltage power supply and gas flow rate, reactor size, distance between electrodes and wall (discharge gap) etc. for the non-thermal plasma reactor. These changes in parameters will result in varying outlet gas compositions and solid carbon properties. Several research groups have already performed similar measurements and modelling. Consequently, the data generated by these researchers will be incorporated into the project wherever necessary, with appropriate citations provided.

A general overview of the data type and how the data is gathered for this project within the consortium is provided in APPENDIX-1.

2. FAIR DATA

2.1. WILL DATA BE IDENTIFIED BY A PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER

2.1.1. WILL DATA BE IDENTIFIED BY A PERSISTENT IDENTIFIER

To ensure data findability, comprehensive descriptions and clear identification are essential. Accordingly, all non-sensitive data and deliverables are made publicly accessible and obtainable through the project repository in [Zenodo](#), each assigned a unique DOI. This practice not only enables immediate access but also renders the datasets citable, thereby enhancing ColdSpark®'s identifiability and visibility within the research community. All data published in Zenodo is accessible through the project's dedicated community, fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing. Creating and managing the project's community encourages researchers to explore additional datasets available there, promotes engagement and facilitates broader scientific inquiry.

Whenever feasible, authors are credited using their ORCID iDs, further enhancing the clarity and accountability of data attribution.

2.1.2. METADATA

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created?

To facilitate data identification, project ColdSpark® employs a framework encompassing metadata definition and keyword assignment, alongside the utilisation of standard identification mechanisms and naming conventions. This ensures a systematic and efficient approach to data management.

Final calibrated data will be accompanied by relevant metadata and keywords, each file possessing a unique identifier to enhance traceability and retrieval.

Publicly available datasets and deliverables hosted on Zenodo.org adhere to the DataCite metadata schema, incorporating the following essential elements:

- Title
- Author
- Date
- DOI
- Keywords
- Description
- License
- Funding
- Access level

What disciplinary or general standards will be followed?

The unique identifier includes the name of the data originator/institute, work package number, parameter, date of measurement, instrument name and version number. Since different scientific communities are participating in this project, the metadata will be distinct from each experiment measurement group and the modelling group. Each partner is responsible for their data, which includes sensitive information measurements depending on the organisation's rules.

2.1.3. KEYWORDS TO BE PROVIDED IN THE METADATA TO OPTIMISE THE POSSIBILITY FOR DISCOVERY AND POTENTIAL RE-USE

Encouraging scientific exploration, discussion, and fostering innovation are the primary objectives of ColdSpark®. Facilitating the re-use of data is an integral part of achieving these goals, as it can potentially lead to the generation of new data. Therefore, the publicly accessible data provided by ColdSpark® include carefully selected keywords to maximise their effective reuse.

Keywords serve as crucial tools for the optimisation of the ColdSpark® project website. They have been carefully chosen and implemented to enhance the visibility and reusability of the data. By strategically incorporating relevant keywords, ColdSpark® aims to facilitate easier discovery and utilisation of its datasets, thereby fostering collaboration, innovation, and advancement within the scientific community.

The selected keywords are provided in D7.3. The keywords will be regularly revised and the list will be updated if necessary.

2.1.4. HOW METADATA CAN BE HARVESTED AND INDEXED

For data that is open and non-confidential, metadata will be employed for identification purposes. This metadata will enhance the discoverability and usability of the data for both internal and external stakeholders.

However, confidential data will be treated differently. While identifiable to consortium partners through standard identification mechanisms, confidential data will not have associated metadata that can be easily harvested or accessed by third parties, as stored and accessible only to authorised consortium members.

Upon project completion, access to confidential data will be restricted further, preventing third-party use. This approach ensures the protection of sensitive information while allowing for effective collaboration and utilisation of non-confidential data within and beyond the ColdSpark® project.

2.2. ACCESSIBLE PROJECT DATA

The following access options and policies remain unchanged from the previous version of the DMP:

OR – Open repository

An Open Access repository ([Zenodo community](#)) has been created to upload publicly available outcomes. Thus, ColdSpark® complies with the requirement of long-term open access to the public results of the project.

PR – Project repository

The project uses a password-protected repository on Microsoft Teams/share point, exploiting the security and backup services of the platform and managed by the project coordinator. Two-level access to the folders is provided to the project partners depending on the level of confidentiality. Specific rules and structure are established in the Project Management Manual (D8.1.)

CR - Company/Institution repository

Each partner organisation uses cloud and offline data storage solutions that must comply with the cybersecurity rules of the company/institution/organisation. The access is limited to the company/institution/organisation employees/contracted staff.

Project Website - www.coldspark.eu

The public data generated by the project (dissemination and communication materials, public deliverables, etc.) are published in open access on the project website (www.coldspark.eu). The project website will remain online for at least 2 years after the end of the project.

European Commission's repository - CORDIS

Public deliverables and results are made available on [CORDIS](#).

The project coordinator, SEID AS, is responsible for centralisation and giving access to the relevant repositories. Each partner is responsible for their data (security measurements depending on internal rules).

2.2.1. DATA DEPOSITION IN A TRUSTED REPOSITORY

All research data and publications that include non-sensitive data are deposited in the ColdSpark® repository in Zenodo, which is a well-established open dissemination research data repository available for data, publications, and software and has been chosen by the project partners as suitable for the project's needs. It is each partner's responsibility to provide and update the repository regularly for each data set. All publications in the repository will be approved by the PMO.

GitHub, a development platform to host and review code and building software will be used as the repository for software. The data generated from OpenScad will also be deposited in GitHub.

2.2.2. ARRANGEMENTS WITH IDENTIFIED REPOSITORIES WHERE THE DATA WILL BE DEPOSITED

Project partners are working with the systems described above. Suggestions for other repositories can be discussed at any time during the project's lifetime, and approval will be given during the official Project Meeting held every 6 months. Special attention is paid that all data management procedures and their implementation are in line with the FAIR principles, to ensure the required access and reuse of data.

2.2.3. DOES THE REPOSITORY ENSURE THAT THE DATA IS ASSIGNED AN IDENTIFIER? WILL THE REPOSITORY RESOLVE THE IDENTIFIER TO A DIGITAL OBJECT?

Zenodo assigns all publicly available data a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). This ensures that the uploaded data is easily citeable. The repository accepts any file format that provides easy storage of data produced.

2.2.4. COLDSPARK® OPENLY AVAILABLE DATA – LEGAL, CONTRACTUAL, INTENTIONAL PARTNER-SPECIFIC RESTRICTIONS

Most data produced within the ColdSpark® project are sensitive and available within the project consortium. Publishable data will be timely deposited in the repository. This will follow the data-sharing policy implemented in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. As stated in the previous version of the DMP:

- Results are owned by the partner that generates them and hence has the right to evaluate these data and assign them whether they are sensitive or not.
- Confidential/sensitive data are available on a confidential level to the European Commission.
- Background i.e., the data, know-how or information needed to implement the action or exploit the results has been given access according to Attachment 1 of the Consortium Agreement.
- All kinds of sharing information, including dissemination, requires consent from the partner who produced the data. Prior notice of any planned publication shall be given to the other Parties (jointly owned results) at least 45 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made as a written notice to the Coordinator and the Party or Parties proposing the dissemination within 30 calendar days after receipt of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit stated above, the publication is permitted.

The objective is to ensure that all non-sensitive data is made publicly available, fostering collaboration and synergies among ColdSpark® partners and other relevant projects and stakeholders. Whenever feasible, efforts will be made to release the data under an open license or into the public domain. Data featured on the ColdSpark® Zenodo community will be readily reusable by external stakeholders interested in the outcomes and findings of the ColdSpark® project, thereby facilitating broader engagement and utilisation of project results.

2.2.5. PERIOD OF AN EMBARGO (IF APPLIED) TO GIVE TIME TO PUBLISH OR SEEK THE PROTECTION OF THE INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY (E.G., PATENTS)

Why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible?

If ColdSpark® deposits sensitive data under an embargo status in a repository, an end date for the embargo will be provided. Under the conditions of Zenodo, these data will be available to the public automatically.

2.2.6. WILL THE DATA BE ACCESSIBLE THROUGH A FREE AND STANDARDIZED ACCESS PROTOCOL?

ColdSpark® data files will be deposited either as closed, open or with embargoed access under the conditions of Zenodo, as the chosen repository. Access to metadata and data is provided through Zenodo, which uses Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) interface.

2.2.7. ACCESS TO THE DATA DURING AND AFTER THE END OF THE PROJECT IF RESTRICTIONS EXIST

Access to sensitive data is limited to project partners, with management overseen by the PMO. Restricted access is enforced for certain data during the project's duration to the relevant partners involved in the specific Work package. In cases where data cannot be shared or must be shared under restrictions, explicit written communication to the consortium outlines legal reasons, as specified in the project Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement.

2.2.8. THE IDENTITY OF THE PERSONS ACCESSING THE DATA IS TO BE ASCERTAINED

Published data will be accessible to everyone without any restrictions or authentication requirements via the project's repositories and project website.

The management of data stored within the ColdSpark® Teams environment is overseen by the PMO. Access to specific institutional accounts is granted upon request from project partners, with the PMO responsible for ensuring appropriate access rights. Additionally, in the event of an individual exiting the project, the PMO takes measures to retrieve access rights to maintain data security and integrity of the project data.

2.2.9. DATA ACCESS COMMITTEE (E.G., TO EVALUATE/APPROVE ACCESS REQUESTS TO PERSONAL/SENSITIVE DATA)

Given the explicit nature of all regulations pertaining to data access, no need has been identified so far for the establishment of a dedicated Data Access Committee. Instead, if needed, decisions regarding data management will be made by the General Assembly, serving as the supreme governing body within the ColdSpark® project.

2.2.10. OPENLY AVAILABLE METADATA AND LICENCED UNDER A PUBLIC DOMAIN DEDICATION CC0, AS PER THE GRANT AGREEMENT

Non-sensitive metadata are made publicly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, in accordance with the terms outlined in the Grant Agreement. These metadata are accessible via OAI-PMH and are available for harvesting: <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>. Metadata of confidential outcomes is not openly available.

2.2.11. HOW LONG WILL THE DATA REMAIN AVAILABLE AND FINDABLE? WILL METADATA BE GUARANTEED TO REMAIN AVAILABLE AFTER DATA IS NO LONGER AVAILABLE?

Currently, Zenodo's retention policy ensures data availability for the lifetime of the repository, which is stated to be at least 20 years ahead: <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>. Should closure of the repository occur for any reason, ColdSpark® partners will endeavour to migrate all available data to suitable alternative institutional and/or subject-based repositories. The data will be stored in file formats that have a high chance of remaining usable and findable for the long term.

Data stored in the project's Teams repository will be retained for as long as the repository remains active and there is a need for data storage. Detailed information on data management practices can be found in the table in Appendix 1.

Metadata may remain available even after data is no longer available.

2.2.12. WILL DOCUMENTATION OR REFERENCES ABOUT ANY SOFTWARE BE NEEDED TO ACCESS OR READ THE DATA BE INCLUDED? WILL IT BE POSSIBLE TO INCLUDE THE RELEVANT SOFTWARE (E.G., IN OPEN-SOURCE CODE)?

All publicly accessible data published as a result of the activities within the ColdSpark® project can be viewed and utilised using widely known software tools. The Consortium strongly favours open-source software solutions. In case specialised software is necessary, the Consortium will provide links to the required software or relevant documentation to facilitate the access and utilisation of the data.

2.3. INTEROPERABLE PROJECT DATA

2.3.1. DATA AND METADATA VOCABULARIES, STANDARDS, FORMATS OR METHODOLOGIES FOR DATA INTEROPERABILITY DATA EXCHANGE AND REUSE WITHIN AND ACROSS DISCIPLINES? WILL YOU FOLLOW COMMUNITY-ENDORSED INTEROPERABILITY BEST PRACTICES? WHICH ONES?

Within the ColdSpark® project community, Zenodo serves as the primary platform for data storage and dissemination. The metadata standards employed align with those provided by Zenodo, ensuring compliance with DataCite's Metadata Schema. In addition, Zenodo's metadata incorporates a few supplementary enrichments that further enhance data discoverability and accessibility within the ColdSpark® project community.

2.3.2. USE OR GENERATION OF UNCOMMON PROJECT-SPECIFIC ONTOLOGIES OR VOCABULARIES AND AVAILABILITY

ColdSpark® will not use or generate uncommon project-specific ontologies.

2.3.3. QUALIFIED REFERENCES TO OTHER DATA

ColdSpark® project reuses qualified references to other data from consortium partners' previous research. In all cases where data reuse extends beyond the project partner's contributions, proper attribution to the source is diligently provided.

2.4. INCREASE DATA RE-USE

2.4.1. HOW DOCUMENTATION WILL BE PROVIDED TO VALIDATE DATA ANALYSIS AND FACILITATE DATA RE-USE

The information is being provided through readme files, analyses, and variable definitions.

2.4.2. AVAILABILITY IN THE PUBLIC DOMAIN TO PERMIT THE WIDEST RE-USE POSSIBLE

Will the data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

All public deliverables are automatically published in the EC public domain, CORDIS and available on the project website and the ColdSpark® community on Zenodo upon approval. To enhance the visibility of our data resources, the [ColdSpark® website](#) features direct links to both CORDIS and Zenodo. These links serve as convenient entry points for stakeholders seeking comprehensive access to our project's datasets and deliverables.

Non-sensitive data produced from ColdSpark® use creative common licences such as CC BY-SA, CC BY-NC or CCO licences depending on the data/document.

2.4.3. WILL THE DATA PRODUCED IN THE PROJECT BE USEABLE BY THIRD PARTIES, IN PARTICULAR AFTER THE END OF THE PROJECT?

All publicly available data and products produced or used in the project are encouraged to be used by third parties as soon as possible. All public data available through the project's open repositories will remain open for reuse after the end of the project.

Additionally, third parties may be allowed to use the data in agreement with the data owner and will have the likelihood to either cite data and publications or offer co-authorship to the data owner.

Data reuse will increase the impact and visibility of the research and will provide credits for the researchers involved, provide resources for training and education, and reduce the costs of duplicating the data. This reuse, however, will be per the Grant Agreement and the Consortium

Agreement.

2.4.4. WILL THE PROVENANCE OF THE DATA BE THOROUGHLY DOCUMENTED USING THE APPROPRIATE STANDARDS?

Yes, the data provenance will be thoroughly documented. This will also provide essential information for determining data quality, transparency, and reliability and will facilitate data reproducibility. This benefits data users, who are usually different from the data producers. Documentation will be regularly updated as needed to reflect any changes or updates to the data and its provenance. This ensures that the data remains accurate and up to date.

2.4.5. DESCRIBE ALL RELEVANT DATA QUALITY ASSURANCE PROCESSES

Each project partner within the Consortium adheres to their established quality assurance procedures, which encompass data calibration in accordance with international standards. Data quality receives special attention during the review checks of all ColdSpark® deliverables, irrespective of whether they are public or confidential. Additionally, the consortium implements versioning of products and data to facilitate their reusability over an extended period.

All public data is stored in the project's data repositories and remains indefinitely accessible and reusable, ensuring continued availability for ongoing and future research endeavours.

2.4.6. FAIR PRINCIPLES, CONSIDERATION OF RESEARCH OUTPUTS OTHER THAN DATA AND ASPECTS RELATED TO THE ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES, DATA SECURITY AND ETHICS

All partners are involved in the development of the Data Management Plan and its updating process and are responsible for ensuring that the documents and files they upload comply with the general guidelines set out in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

3. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

3.1. MANAGEMENT OF OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS THAT MAY BE GENERATED OR RE-USED THROUGHOUT THEIR PROJECTS

Partners within the ColdSpark® project deliver datasets and metadata generated or collected during the project, adhering to the guidelines outlined in Annex 1 (in Grant Agreement). The project coordinator leads the ongoing updating of the Data Management Plan (DMP) and ensures that all partners comply with the documented rules. These efforts aim to maintain consistency and integrity in data management practices throughout the duration of the project and enhance the data reuse after the project's lifetime.

3.2. FAIR DATA PRINCIPLES AND MANAGEMENT OF OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

Agreements on standards, quality level and sharing practices are defined within the consortium.

4. ALLOCATION OF RESOURCES

4.1. COSTS FOR MAKING DATA OR OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS FAIR

All costs associated with resource allocation, data security, and ethical considerations are planned in the project budget. These expenses are covered by the EU funding and allocated through the dedicated budget of each project partner. This process ensures that all necessary measures to safeguard data, maintain security protocols, and uphold ethical standards are adequately financed and continuously implemented throughout the project lifetime.

4.2. DM RESPONSIBILITIES

According to the ColdSpark® Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement, the partner generating the data retains its ownership and assumes accountability for its access and storage. Data owners should upload without delay and maintain datasets in accordance with the project's quality standards. The coordinator oversees the data management process, which is a dedicated task in the project's implementation (WP 8, Task 8.3), with SEID AS and Europroject Ltd. as responsible partners.

Data and publications intended for open access must undergo review and approval by the coordinator before being uploaded to the repository. All partners receive written notification 45 days in advance to review the data/publications, with a subsequent 30-day window provided for feedback submission. This review process ensures that no sensitive data related to the intellectual property rights of any project partner is disclosed to the public.

4.3. LONG-TERM PRESERVATION, NECESSARY RESOURCES AND DECISION-MAKING

During the ColdSpark® project, public data is available in the project's Zenodo community, which ensures its long preservation. All sensitive data is stored in the project's Teams repository and backed in the internal repositories of the Irgang involved in the project.

5. DATA SECURITY

5.1. PROVISIONS FOR DATA SECURITY (INCLUDING DATA RECOVERY AS WELL AS SECURE STORAGE/ARCHIVING AND TRANSFER OF SENSITIVE DATA)

As stated in the previous version of the DMP, the project coordinator uses Microsoft 365 Business premium with storage in Europe and has an online backup solution. Also, they use extra security and backup from EMP Secure. A two-factor security on user accounts is implemented. Raw data is archived on a local server in the partner's lab, calibrated data is shared through Microsoft Teams and SharePoint.

5.2. SAFELY STORED DATA IN TRUSTED REPOSITORIES FOR LONG-TERM PRESERVATION AND CURATION

ColdSpark® stores public data in Zenodo. According to their policy, data files and metadata are backed up nightly and replicated into multiple copies in the online system.

6. ETHICS

6.1. ETHICS OR LEGAL ISSUES THAT CAN HAVE AN IMPACT ON DATA SHARING

No ethical issues are expected from the data generated in the ColdSpark® project.

6.2. INFORMED CONSENT FOR DATA SHARING AND LONG-TERM PRESERVATION

All partners responsible for collecting confidential data adhere to strict protocols for archiving on secured internal servers. Sharing of confidential data is restricted in accordance with the provisions outlined in the ColdSpark® Consortium Agreement. These measures are designed to maintain the confidentiality and integrity of sensitive information while upholding legal and ethical standards regarding data protection and privacy.

The collection and processing of personal data, such as email addresses used for newsletters sharing and data collected during ColdSpark® events, are conducted in accordance with Regulation 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016, commonly known as the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), as well as relevant national legislations. Comprehensive measures are implemented to ensure compliance with these regulations and to safeguard the data privacy of all individuals.

7. OTHER ISSUES

ColdSpark® will not use other national/funder/sectorial /departmental procedures for DM.

APPENDIX 1: DATA COLLECTED, PRODUCED AND REUSED IN THE COLDSPARK® PROJECT

Partner	Data Type	Data gathered by
SEID AS	Plasma electrical signals, power supply parameters (Voltage, current, frequency), gas analysis data, emission spectra, reactor performance parameters (gas flow rate, electrode configuration (electrode shape, distance between the electrode and the reactor wall), reaction sets	Oscilloscope, gas Chromatography (GC), Spectrometer, data analysis, modelling, COMSOL Multiphysics
University of Stavanger	Gas-solid equilibrium analysis, carbon characterization data, dynamic study on gas separation, Adsorbent Characteristics	Gas sorption instrument, scanning electron microscope (SEM), Transmission electron microscopy (TEM), Raman Spectroscopy, X-ray diffraction (XRD), surface area, Gas separation test instrument, powder diffraction (PXR), thermogravimetric analysis (TGA), surface area
NORCE	Aspen HYSYS	Modelling data
University of Liverpool	Plasma electrical signals, gas analysis data, carbon characterisation, emission spectra, reaction performance, reaction sets	Oscilloscope, GC, SEM, TEM, Raman Spectroscopy, XRD, and spectrometer, analysis of collected data, modelling, data previously collected include reaction rate constants from the literature
IREC	Quantities of material and energy flows and yields, technical specifications of equipment (power rates, operating times, efficiencies), compositions in weight % of the mass, volume % (v%), ppm, recyclability rates, databased (foreground data), the composition of H ₂ streams, pressure, temperature	Research and literature revision (Background data), Foreground data by filling templates from experts in the core technology, GaBi Professional databases. Data is previously collected from scientific journals and other recognized sources, recognized reports, EU reports, and other recognized sources, readable documentation source

IBBK	Participation in dissemination events, workshops	Market analysis, Dissemination of results
EuroProject	Publicly available data from the European Commission's public repository CORDIS in relation to the involvement of other projects, initiatives, and stakeholders and from other publicly available sources; EP may use data from stock image banks	Research, Market analysis, Dissemination of results (gather data from the workshops conducted)